

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

Climate drives anuran breeding phenology in a continental perspective as revealed by citizen-collected data

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Table S1. List of anuran species in Brazil identified to the species level in the iNaturalist database with their reproductive strategy (explosive, prolonged or not known). A continuous or intermediate breeding have been categorised as prolonged and opportunistic breeding has been categorised as explosive. Reproductive patterns marked with an * are based on the period of reproduction described in the text of the reference

Species	Reproduction	References
<i>Adelphobates castaneoticus</i>	N/A	
<i>Adelphobates galactonotus</i>	N/A	
<i>Adelphobates quinquevittatus</i>	N/A	
<i>Adenomera andreae</i>	prolonged	MOREIRA and LIMA, 1991
<i>Adenomera diptyx</i>	prolonged	SOUSA et al., 2019
<i>Adenomera hylaedactyla</i>	prolonged	SOUSA et al., 2019
<i>Adenomera marmorata</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Adenomera nana</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Allobates femoralis</i>	prolonged	KAEFER et al., 2012
<i>Allobates nunciatus</i>	prolonged*	MORAES et al., 2019
<i>Allobates sumtuosus</i>	N/A	
<i>Allobates tapajos</i>	N/A	
<i>Allophryne ruthveni</i>	N/A	
<i>Amazophrynella manaos</i>	N/A	
<i>Ameerega berohoka</i>	N/A	
<i>Ameerega braccata</i>	N/A	
<i>Ameerega flavopicta</i>	N/A	
<i>Ameerega hahneli</i>	N/A	
<i>Ameerega munduruku</i>	N/A	
<i>Ameerega trivittata</i>	N/A	
<i>Anomaloglossus stepheni</i>	N/A	
<i>Aplastodiscus albosignatus</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Aplastodiscus arildae</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Aplastodiscus ehrhardti</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Aplastodiscus leucopygius</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Aplastodiscus perviridis</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Atelopus hoogmoedi</i>	N/A	
<i>Barycholos ternetzi</i>	N/A	
<i>Boana albomarginata</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Boana albopunctata</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021

Species	Reproduction	References
<i>Boana bischoffi</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Boana boans</i>	prolonged*	LIMA et al., 2006
<i>Boana caingua</i>	prolonged*	ESTEVES, 2012
<i>Boana calcarata</i>	N/A	
<i>Boana cinerascens</i>	N/A	
<i>Boana crepitans</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Boana exastis</i>	N/A	
<i>Boana faber</i>	prolonged	TOLEDO et al. 2003
<i>Boana geographica</i>	prolonged*	LIMA et al., 2006
<i>Boana guentheri</i>	N/A	
<i>Boana joaquina</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Boana lanciformis</i>	prolonged	LIMA et al., 2006
<i>Boana leptolineata</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Boana leucocheila</i>	N/A	
<i>Boana lundii</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Boana multifasciata</i>	prolonged	
<i>Boana paranaiba</i>	N/A	
<i>Boana pardalis</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Boana polytaenia</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Boana prasina</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Boana pulchella</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Boana punctata</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Boana raniceps</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Boana semilineata</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Boana xerophylla</i>	N/A	
<i>Bokermannohyla alvarengai</i>	N/A	
<i>Bokermannohyla circumdata</i>	explosive	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Bokermannohyla hylax</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Bokermannohyla sapiranga</i>	N/A	
<i>Brachycephalus ephippium</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Brachycephalus pitanga</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Callimedusa tomopterna</i>	N/A	
<i>Ceratophrys cornuta</i>	explosive	ULLOA et al. 2019
<i>Chiasmocleis albopunctata</i>	explosive	TOLEDO et al. 2003
<i>Chiasmocleis avilapiresae</i>	N/A	
<i>Chiasmocleis bassleri</i>	N/A	
<i>Crossodactylus caramaschii</i>	prolonged*	TEIXEIRA, 2009
<i>Crossodactylus gaudichaudii</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Crossodactylus schmidti</i>	N/A	
<i>Cycloramphus acangatan</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Cycloramphus eleutherodactylus</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Dendrobates tinctorius</i>	N/A	
<i>Dendrophryniscus berthalutzae</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Dendropsophus anceps</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Dendropsophus berthalutzae</i>	explosive	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Dendropsophus bipunctatus</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Dendropsophus branneri</i>	prolonged*	AMORIM, 2009

Species	Reproduction	References
<i>Dendropsophus cruzi</i>	prolonged	KOPP et al., 2010
<i>Dendropsophus decipiens</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Dendropsophus elegans</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Dendropsophus elianae</i>	prolonged	SOUSA et al., 2019 / SANTOS et al., 2007
<i>Dendropsophus jimi</i>	prolonged	KOPP et al., 2010
<i>Dendropsophus leucophyllatus</i>	prolonged	
<i>Dendropsophus marmoratus</i>	N/A	
<i>Dendropsophus melanargyreus</i>	N/A	
<i>Dendropsophus microcephalus</i>	prolonged	
<i>Dendropsophus microps</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Dendropsophus minusculus</i>	N/A	
<i>Dendropsophus minutus</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021 / LEIVAS et al., 2018 / KOPP et al., 2010
<i>Dendropsophus nanus</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Dendropsophus rubicundulus</i>	prolonged	BATISTA, 2018
<i>Dendropsophus sanborni</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Dendropsophus soaresi</i>	explosive	AMORIM, 2009
<i>Dendropsophus werneri</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Dermatonotus muelleri</i>	explosive*	AMORIM, 2009
<i>Elachistocleis bicolor</i>	explosive	OLIVEIRA, 2021 / RODRIGUES et al., 2003
<i>Elachistocleis cesarii</i>	explosive	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Elachistocleis helianneae</i>	N/A	
<i>Elachistocleis matogrosso</i>	N/A	
<i>Engystomops freibergeri</i>	N/A	
<i>Gastrotheca fissipes</i>	N/A	
<i>Haddadus binotatus</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Hamptophryne boliviana</i>	N/A	
<i>Hyalinobatrachium cappellei</i>	N/A	
<i>Hyalinobatrachium mondolfii</i>	N/A	
<i>Hylodes asper</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Hylodes fredei</i>	N/A	
<i>Hylodes heyeri</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Hylodes meridionalis</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Hylodes nasus</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Hylodes perplicatus</i>	N/A	
<i>Hylodes phyllodes</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Hylodes sazimai</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Hylodes uai</i>	N/A	
<i>Ischnocnema guentheri</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Ischnocnema henselii</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Ischnocnema juipoca</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Ischnocnema parva</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Itapotihyla langsdorffii</i>	explosive	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Leptodactylus fuscus</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021 / KOPP et al., 2010 / PRADO et al., 2005

Species	Reproduction	References
<i>Leptodactylus gracilis</i>	prolonged	MATA, 2015
<i>Leptodactylus jolyi</i>	N/A	
<i>Leptodactylus knudseni</i>	prolonged*	LIMA et al., 2006
<i>Leptodactylus labyrinthicus</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Leptodactylus latrans</i>	prolonged	MATA, 2015
<i>Leptodactylus macrosternum</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Leptodactylus mystaceus</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Leptodactylus mystacinus</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Leptodactylus natalensis</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Leptodactylus notoaktites</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Leptodactylus paraensis</i>	N/A	
<i>Leptodactylus pentadactylus</i>	prolonged*	LIMA et al., 2006
<i>Leptodactylus petersii</i>	prolonged*	LIMA et al., 2006
<i>Leptodactylus plaumanni</i>	N/A	
<i>Leptodactylus podicipinus</i>	prolonged/explosive	OLIVEIRA, 2021; SANTOS et al., 2007; PRADO et al., 2005 / KOPP et al., 2010
<i>Leptodactylus rhodomystax</i>	prolonged*	LIMA et al., 2006
<i>Leptodactylus riveroi</i>	prolonged*	LIMA et al., 2006
<i>Leptodactylus syphax</i>	N/A	
<i>Leptodactylus troglodytes</i>	prolonged*	PROTÁZIO et al., 2015 / AMORIM, 2009
<i>Leptodactylus vastus</i>	N/A	
<i>Limnomedusa macroglossa</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Lithobates catesbeianus</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Lithobates palmipes</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Lithodytes lineatus</i>	N/A	
<i>Lysapsus limellum</i>	N/A	
<i>Macrogenioglottus alipioi</i>	explosive	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Melanophryniscus atroluteus</i>	N/A	
<i>Melanophryniscus dorsalis</i>	explosive	
<i>Melanophryniscus fulvoguttatus</i>	N/A	
<i>Melanophryniscus moreirae</i>	N/A	
<i>Melanophryniscus spectabilis</i>	N/A	
<i>Melanophryniscus tumifrons</i>	N/A	
<i>Nyctimantis brunoi</i>	explosive	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Odontophrynus americanus</i>	explosive	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Odontophrynus cultripes</i>	N/A	
<i>Osteocephalus leprieurii</i>	explosive	GOTTSBERGER and GRUBER, 2001
<i>Osteocephalus oophagus</i>	N/A	
<i>Osteocephalus planiceps</i>	N/A	
<i>Osteocephalus taurinus</i>	prolonged*	LIMA et al., 2006
<i>Phasmahyla guttata</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Phyllodytes edelmoi</i>	N/A	
<i>Phyllodytes luteolus</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Phyllomedusa bahiana</i>	N/A	

Species	Reproduction	References
<i>Phyllomedusa bicolor</i>	prolonged*	LIMA et al., 2006
<i>Phyllomedusa burmeisteri</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Phyllomedusa camba</i>	N/A	
<i>Phyllomedusa distincta</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Phyllomedusa iheringii</i>	N/A	
<i>Phyllomedusa tetraploidea</i>	N/A	
<i>Phyllomedusa vaillantii</i>	prolonged*	LIMA et al., 2006
<i>Physalaemus albonotatus</i>	prolonged	PRADO et al., 2005 / CAJADE et al., 2020
<i>Physalaemus atlanticus</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Physalaemus biligonigerus</i>	prolonged	MATA, 2015
<i>Physalaemus centralis</i>	explosive	KOPP et al., 2010
<i>Physalaemus cicada</i>	prolonged	PROTÁZIO et al., 2015
<i>Physalaemus crombiei</i>	N/A	
<i>Physalaemus cuvieri</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021 / KOPP et al., 2010
<i>Physalaemus ephippifer</i>	N/A	
<i>Physalaemus gracilis</i>	prolonged	MATA, 2015
<i>Physalaemus henselii</i>	prolonged	MATA, 2015
<i>Physalaemus kroyeri</i>	prolonged	GALLY and ZINA, 2013
<i>Physalaemus lateristriga</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Physalaemus lisei</i>	N/A	
<i>Physalaemus moreirae</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Physalaemus nanus</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Physalaemus nattereri</i>	explosive	RODRIGUES et al. 2004
<i>Physalaemus olfersii</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Physalaemus riograndensis</i>	N/A	
<i>Physalaemus signifer</i>	explosive*	ABRUNHOSA et al., 2006
<i>Physalaemus spiniger</i>	explosive	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Pipa pipa</i>	prolonged*	LIMA et al., 2006
<i>Pithecopus azureus</i>	explosive	SOUSA et al., 2019
<i>Pithecopus hypochondrialis</i>	N/A	
<i>Pithecopus nordestinus</i>	prolonged	FARAULO et al., 2019
<i>Pleurodema diplolister</i>	explosive	SOUSA and ÁVILA, 2005 / PROTÁZIO et al., 2015
<i>Pristimantis fenestratus</i>	N/A	
<i>Pristimantis paulodutraii</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Pristimantis ramagii</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Proceratophrys bigibbosa</i>	N/A	
<i>Proceratophrys boiei</i>	prolonged	BERTOLUCI, 1998
<i>Proceratophrys brauni</i>	prolonged*	SANTOS and CONTE, 2014
<i>Proceratophrys cristiceps</i>	N/A	
<i>Proceratophrys laticeps</i>	N/A	
<i>Proceratophrys renalis</i>	N/A	
<i>Proceratophrys subguttata</i>	N/A	
<i>Pseudis platensis</i>	N/A	
<i>Pseudopaludicola canga</i>	N/A	

Species	Reproduction	References
<i>Pseudopaludicola falcipes</i>	prolonged	
<i>Pseudopaludicola matuta</i>	N/A	
<i>Pseudopaludicola pocoto</i>	N/A	
<i>Rhaebo guttatus</i>	explosive	MACHADO and BERNARDE, 2011
<i>Rhinella arenarum</i>	N/A	
<i>Rhinella castaneotica</i>	N/A	
<i>Rhinella crucifer</i>	explosive	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Rhinella diptycha</i>	explosive	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Rhinella granulosa</i>	explosive	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Rhinella henseli</i>	N/A	
<i>Rhinella hoogmoedi</i>	explosive	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Rhinella icterica</i>	explosive	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Rhinella major</i>	N/A	
<i>Rhinella margaritifera</i>	N/A	
<i>Rhinella marina</i>	explosive*	MACHADO and BERNARDE, 2011
<i>Rhinella mirandaribeiroi</i>	N/A	
<i>Rhinella ornata</i>	explosive	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Rhinella proboscidea</i>	N/A	
<i>Rhinella pygmaea</i>	explosive	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Rhinella rubescens</i>	N/A	
<i>Scinax acuminatus</i>	explosive	PRADO et al., 2005
<i>Scinax agilis</i>	N/A	
<i>Scinax alter</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Scinax argyreornatus</i>	explosive	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Scinax auratus</i>	N/A	
<i>Scinax crospedospilus</i>	explosive	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Scinax cruentomma</i>	N/A	
<i>Scinax cuspidatus</i>	explosive	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Scinax eurydice</i>	explosive	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Scinax flavoguttatus</i>	explosive	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Scinax fuscovarius</i>	explosive	OLIVEIRA, 2021 / KOPP et al., 2010
<i>Scinax garbei</i>	prolonged*	LIMA et al., 2006
<i>Scinax granulatus</i>	prolonged	MATA, 2015
<i>Scinax hayii</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Scinax imbegue</i>	prolonged*	SANTOS and CONTE, 2014
<i>Scinax littoralis</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Scinax longilineus</i>	explosive	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Scinax nasicus</i>	explosive	PRADO et al., 2005
<i>Scinax nebulosus</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Scinax obtriangulatus</i>	N/A	
<i>Scinax perereca</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Scinax perpusillus</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Scinax rizibilis</i>	explosive	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Scinax rossaferesae</i>	N/A	

Species	Reproduction	References
<i>Scinax ruber</i>	prolonged*	LIMA et al., 2006
<i>Scinax squalirostris</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Scinax tripui</i>	N/A	
<i>Scinax tropicalia</i>	N/A	
<i>Scinax tymbamirim</i>	prolonged	MATA, 2015
<i>Scinax x-signatus</i>	explosive	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Sphaenorhynchus caramaschii</i>	N/A	
<i>Sphaenorhynchus lacteus</i>	N/A	
<i>Sphaenorhynchus planicola</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Sphaenorhynchus surdus</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Thoropa megatympanum</i>	N/A	
<i>Thoropa miliaris</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Thoropa taophora</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Trachycephalus mesophaeus</i>	explosive	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Trachycephalus nigromaculatus</i>	explosive	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Trachycephalus resinifictrix</i>	N/A	
<i>Trachycephalus typhonius</i>	explosive	OLIVEIRA, 2021
<i>Vitreorana uranoscopa</i>	prolonged	OLIVEIRA, 2021

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